

An Investigation into the Incidence of Numeracy Advice in Early Years Education-Focused Inspections in the Republic of Ireland

Sandra O’Neill

Dublin City University

Since 2015 Early Childhood Care and Education settings in the Republic of Ireland have been subject to Early Years Education-focused Inspections (EYEI). These inspections have been identified as a way of identifying good practice and improving outcomes for children in relation to numeracy. This study undertook a textual analysis of the most recent EYEI reports to explore how often numeracy is referred to, and what type of actions are advised to promote and support improvements in practice. The results show that while numeracy is referred to regularly within the reports, advice is less frequent. When offered, advice often advocates for the discontinuation of practice deemed inappropriate rather than suggesting actions that could enhance teaching and learning in relation to mathematics.

Introduction

Children possess an innate capacity for mathematics (National Research Council [U.S.], 2009) and demonstrate an interest in math in their play, daily routines and interactions. Early mathematics skills and knowledge have been found to be the greatest predictor of later academic achievement regardless of the sex or socio-economic background of the child (Duncan et al., 2007) and are stronger predictor of later school success than tests of intelligence or memory (Krajewski & Schneider, 2009). Consequently, numeracy has emerged as a policy focus in early childhood care and education (ECCE). In the Republic of Ireland (RoI), Early Years Education-focused Inspections (EYEI) carried out by the Department of Education and Skills (DES) began in 2015. Early years settings providing the State-funded ECCE scheme for children from 2 years 8 months until they enrol in primary school, are subject to these inspections. This study is concerned with the regularity with which numeracy is commented on in EYEI reports, and the type and depth advice that is given to improve practice. Research questions posed include: How often do inspection reports refer to numeracy? How often is advice issued? How detailed is the advice? and finally, what level of uniformity exists in advice and comments?

The Emergence of Early Childhood Mathematics Policy

Since 2017 a number of policy developments have led to a focus on early childhood mathematics (ECM) in RoI. The interim review of the national literacy and numeracy strategy has laid out updated targets for ECCE, claiming that a stronger focus on numeracy is warranted and the re-invigoration of numeracy through everyday practice in ECCE settings is required (DES, 2017a). A key priority action is to ‘support practitioners in ECCE settings... to gain a deeper understanding of numeracy concepts, the sequence in which children learn early mathematical ideas and identifying and providing materials and activities which further promote learning in this area’ (DES, 2017a, p. 21). The strategy identifies the EYEI as a mechanism to support and promote improvements in the ECCE sector, and targets the

upskilling of ECCE educators through multiple means including; the Better Start National Quality Development Service; the Aistear Síolta Practice Guide (www.aistearsiolta.ie) and EYEIs. Specifically, the strategy states that the ‘Inspection team evaluates current numeracy provision in early years settings...[and] provides guidance and advice to practitioners to ensure that children have daily exposure to key early numeracy concepts, experiences and materials’ (DES, 2017a, p.28). In addition, since 2017 a focus on STEM policy (DES, 2017b; DES, 2017c; DES, 2020) has brought further attention to ECM. The EYEI tool was updated in 2018 and now includes explicit criteria related to numeracy, math thinking and learning (DES, 2018). Settings are now required to provide numeracy opportunities and are inspected accordingly.

The Role of the Educator

ECCE educators in Ireland must hold a minimum level 5 qualification¹. Numeracy is often included at level 5 and 6, and in degree programmes. However, anecdotal evidence suggests that attention to ECM in initial education is rudimentary. Within the social pedagogy tradition of ECCE ‘discovery maths’ is the preferable approach. This is where maths experiences are informal in nature, embedded in children’s free play and where learning occurs incidentally rather than intentionally (Thiel & Perry, 2018). Many educators, including those lecturing in higher education, are uncomfortable with the concept of teaching as traditionally, their role is as that of a play partner. This impacts how and what ECCE educators are taught in their initial education. While graduates report greater confidence, educators holding all levels of qualifications in Ireland state that their initial training is not preparing them to support children’s numeracy skills (DES, 2016). This is unsurprising, as teaching mathematics in pre-school is a complex task. Math-related pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) in preschool involves a number of components. ECCE educators must be able to notice mathematical situations in which children engage, interpret the nature of the math activity and have the knowledge to enhance children’s mathematical thinking and understanding (Lee, 2017). These complex skills cannot be gained through a focus on discovery math in initial education. There is, therefore, considerable scope for developments in thinking about the numeracy preparation of ECCE educators (Dunphy, 2018).

Method

To explore how the inspection process affirms good practice and provides advice on the development or improvement of numeracy, a textual analysis of the 200 most recent EYEI inspection reports was carried out in early 2021. The reports are publically available via DES’ website (www.education.ie) and relate to inspection visits that occurred between 22nd November 2019 and 28th February 2020. EYEIs are based on a quality framework against which inspections are conducted (DES, 2018). The framework includes four broad areas: 1) Quality of the context to support children’s learning and development; 2) Quality of the

¹ See [https://www.qqi.ie/Articles/Pages/National-Framework-of-Qualifications-\(NFQ\).aspx](https://www.qqi.ie/Articles/Pages/National-Framework-of-Qualifications-(NFQ).aspx) for details

processes to support children’s learning and development; 3) Quality of children’s learning experiences and achievements; 4) Quality of management and leadership for learning. Inspection reports are structured using these headings, broken down further into 20 outcomes and ‘signposts for practice’. Table 1 identifies the outcomes and the signposts for practice that relate to numeracy. Area 1 and 4 are excluded as they do not contain explicit outcomes or signposts in relation to this topic. Each report was analysed in the following stages; 1) Review of Area 2 of to identify reference to numeracy; 2) Review of Area 3 of to identify reference to numeracy; 3) Automated search of the full report for key terms; numeracy, math*, shape, space, measure, count, pattern, number; 4) a final scan of each report searching for reference to numeracy. Bullet points that referenced numeracy, math or key terms were copied and stored for further analysis, noting the area in the report from which this information was drawn. A secondary thematic analysis was carried out on this data to uncover uniformity within comments and advice (using Braun & Clarke, 2006).

Table 1*Numeracy –related outcomes and signpost for practice from the EYEI Framework*

Area	Outcome	Signpost for Practice
2 - Quality of processes to support children’s learning and development	Outcome 9 – Emergent language, literacy and numeracy skills are fostered	Practitioners model appropriate language, including mathematical language, and encourage an expanded use of vocabulary through the use of open-ended questioning and language enrichment during interactions Mathematical thinking and learning is promoted through the use of open-ended resources and games, linked to the everyday lives of children It is evident that children have opportunities to engage with activities that build early positive dispositions towards science, technology, engineering, the arts and mathematics
3 – Quality of children’s learning experiences and achievements	Outcome 15 - Children Communicate their experiences, thoughts, ideas and feelings with others in a variety of ways	Children explore sound, pattern, rhythm and repetition in language Children demonstrate an awareness and emergent understanding of the meaning and uses of symbols, pictures, print and numbers as a means of communication Children have a growing understanding of the meaning and use of mathematical language

Note. Area 1 and 4 are excluded as neither contain specific outcomes or signposts relating to numeracy

Findings

80% of the sample reports include reference to numeracy. As expected, comments appear most regularly in in area 2 and area 3, with two examples in area 4. Often the comments have significant uniformity and use similar language. For example, reference to literacy and numeracy are often grouped together in comments

The children's early literacy and numeracy skills are well supported through the use of songs, rhymes and the range of play materials (area 2, report 2)

The children's language, literacy and numeracy skills are fostered well through the use of songs, rhymes and action games (area 2, report 72)

46% of the sample were found to provide specific examples from practice rather than the standardised comments listed above. Examples identified both positive and negative practice

The practitioners use effective strategies to support the development of the children's early numeracy skills. For example, during inspection two children were supported to guess how many blocks it would take to create an arch and then they were supported to count the blocks upon completion, testing their hypothesis (report 164)

Montessori resources were regularly referred to as a way of supporting numeracy, and appeared in approximately 11% of sample reports. It is difficult to decipher in some examples what exactly the named materials are supporting; language, literacy or numeracy

Pre-literacy and pre-numeracy skills as well as emergent language skills are fostered very effectively through the use of the Montessori materials (area 2, report 41)

Montessori mathematical materials promote high-quality mathematical thinking and learning (area 2, report 115)

Actions for improvement were found in 22% of reports. A number of themes emerged when this subset was analysed. Firstly, almost half of the actions advised (44%) related to discontinuing formal teaching practices. Again, literacy and numeracy are grouped in these comments

Formal teaching of literacy and numeracy concepts needs to be replaced by alternative approaches. (report 116)

The practitioners are advised to discontinue the use of worksheets to promote children's literacy and numeracy skills. (report 160)

In a small number of instances, advice is phrased more positively suggesting actions that can improve practice

Numeracy skills are fostered naturally in play. Practitioners focus on concepts such as height when the children are playing with bricks and volume when they are playing with water and sand (report 45)

A second theme that emerged from this subset was the guidance to add further materials that could support numeracy (34% of reports)

The addition of a range of resources such as weighing scales, cookery books and measuring tapes would support the development of early numeracy skills through playful strategies. (report 200)

Overall, there were very few references to mathematical content areas in the reports. No reference was found to pattern or space in a mathematical context. Reference to shape appeared in 12% of reports; capacity appeared in 1%; and sorting, matching and classifying appeared in 1%. Finally, it should be noted that 1% of the sample could not be analysed as the incorrect report was uploaded to education.ie.

Discussion and Conclusion

Reference to numeracy appears in 80% of the reports sampled. However, the vague uniform comments, coupling of literacy and numeracy, and negative framing of some comments does little to provide guidance to ensure children's 'daily exposure to key early numeracy concepts, experiences and materials' (DES, 2017a, p.28). Specific examples from practice that identify everyday math are more powerful and demonstrative when educators are unsure about ECM. The comment 'during water play practitioners could discuss concepts such as weight, temperature, sinking and floating, during their engagement with children. This will support meaningful opportunities for children to engage with experiences that build positive dispositions towards mathematical understanding and skills. (report 27)' is a better illustration of how practice can be improved than 'practitioners are encouraged to increase their use of mathematical vocabulary during their interactions' (report 118). The Literacy and Numeracy Strategy Interim report states that maths concepts such as 'number words and symbols, shapes, counting, patterns, spatial awareness, measurement and data analysis' (DES, 2017, p.28) should be supported, but there was very little reference to these concepts in the reports. It is unclear whether this indicates that practice related to these concepts aren't being demonstrated or simply not being captured. However, with many ECCE educators stating that they are not prepared to support numeracy, more explicit advice is warranted in all reports.

Most early years inspectors hold an ECCE qualification within the social pedagogy tradition that favours discovery math. The concept of teacher as a play partner places a higher value on the learning environment as a 'third teacher' and could explain why over 33% of advice relates to the addition of further numeracy materials. However, this advice will do little to support educators to understand how and why materials are used to improve numeracy practice and outcomes. The relatively high number of references to Montessori materials could be explained in a number of ways; items such as the pink tower or number rods are immediately identifiable in the environment; inspectors are Montessori trained; or a further indication of the focus on materials rather than pedagogy or educators' PCK. Research suggests that ECCE settings in RoI are increasingly using formal approaches to support the development of academic skills (Ring et al., 2016). This study provides further evidence that this is the case. A significant proportion of the advice included in the reports dictate that

formal approaches to numeracy are discontinued. It is evident that ECCE educators are trying to support numeracy in the best way they know how, but many educators require more explicit supports. The DES (2017a) also identified the Aistear Síolta Practice Guide (ASPG) as a support to upskill educators as it includes resources and self-study guides on mathematics. Reference to ASPG appears in relation to environment, assessment and transition but not to numeracy. It could be argued that neglecting to advise settings to access and use these materials is a further missed opportunity to help educators upskill.

Finally, changes in complex domains such as ECM rarely happen without inducement (Newton & Alexander, 2013). The inspectorate is in a privileged position to influence numeracy practice in ECCE settings. More explicit examples, with clear reference to numeracy *independent of literacy* will help identify good practice. A focus on pedagogy and PCK will lead to a more effective inspection process and improve outcomes for children.

References

- Braun, V. & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.
- DES (2016). *Survey of early years practitioners*. DES.
- DES (2017a). *National strategy: Literacy and numeracy for learning and life interim review: 2011-2016 New targets: 2017-2020*. DES.
- DES (2017b). *STEM education policy statement 2017-2026*. DES.
- DES (2017c). *STEM education implementation plan 2017-2019*. DES
- DES (2018). *A guide to early years education inspection (EYEI)*. DES.
- Duncan, G., Dowsett, C. J., Claessens, A., Magnuson, K., ...Duckworth, K. (2007). School readiness and later achievement. *Developmental Psychology*, 43(6), 1428–1446
- Dunphy, E. (2018). Transition from preschool to primary school. Optimising opportunities for mathematics learning. *Education Matters, 2017-2018, 105-110*.
- Krajewski, K., & Schneider, W. (2009). Early development of quantity to number-word linkage as a precursor of mathematical school achievement and mathematical difficulties. *Learning and Instruction*, 19(6), 513–526.
- Lee, J. E. (2017). Preschool teachers' pedagogical content knowledge in mathematics. *International Journal of Early Childhood*, 49(4), 229–243
- National Research Council [NRC] (2009). *Mathematics learning in early childhood: paths toward excellence and equity*. The National Academies Press.
- Ring, E., Mhic Mhathúna, M., Moloney, M., ...Ozonyia, M. (2016). *An examination of concepts of school readiness among parents and educators in Ireland*. Department of Children and Youth Affairs.

Thiel, O. & Perry, B. (2018). Innovative approaches in early childhood mathematics. *Early European Childhood Education Research Journal*, 26(4), 463-468.

Newton, K. & Alexander P. (2013). Early Mathematics Learning in Perspective. In L. English, & J. Mulligan (Eds.), *Reconceptualising early mathematics learning* (pp.5-28). Springer